

Title IV-D Performance Incentives and Shared Parenting Outcomes:

A Policy Analysis

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Author Note This policy analysis synthesizes empirical, historical, and legal scholarship on Title IV-D child support enforcement. No conflicts of interest are declared.

Abstract

Title IV-D of the Social Security Act (1975) funds state child support enforcement through federal matching of administrative costs and performance incentives allocated from a capped national pool tied to five metrics. The program has been effective in increasing paternity establishment rates above 90% and generating more than \$30 billion in annual collections. However, the structure of the incentive system could create financial pressures affecting custody policy and child support guideline design. The review considers the historical development of Title IV-D, the structure of its performance incentives, data from variations across states, and procedural critiques from legal scholarship. I assess policy options, considering their feasibility and potential impact on shared parenting arrangements. Recalibrating incentives and strengthening proportional support guidelines may better align program objectives with contemporary family structures.

Keywords: Title IV-D, child support enforcement, family policy, shared parenting, performance incentives

Introduction

Title IV-D established a federal–state partnership for child support enforcement, providing states federal reimbursement for administrative costs along with performance incentive payments from a fixed national pool. In fiscal year (FY) 2023, performance incentives totaled approximately \$532 million while total program expenditures exceeded \$5 billion annually (U.S. Congress, 2023). States qualify for incentive payments through five performance metrics: paternity establishment, support order establishment, current collections, arrearages collections, and cost-effectiveness (Child Support Performance and Incentive Act of 1998).

The program has significantly expanded enforcement capabilities. National collections increased from approximately \$10 billion in 1998 to more than \$30 billion annually in recent years (Solomon-Fears, 2013). Paternity establishment rates also exceed 90% nationally in many reporting years (Office of Child Support Enforcement, 2023). These outcomes reflect significant administrative expansion and technological modernization of enforcement systems.

Simultaneously, questions arise about how the incentive structure may interact with family law policy. Since multiple metrics depend on support collections, custody arrangements that reduce formal support obligations could indirectly affect program performance. In many states, joint custody arrangements can lower formal support obligations. I consider how Title IV-D incentives might create institutional pressures affecting custody outcomes and shared parenting arrangements.

Historical Development

Prior to 1975, child support enforcement was largely a state responsibility. Interstate enforcement was limited by mechanisms such as the Uniform Reciprocal Enforcement of Support Act (1950), which relied on cooperation between courts in different jurisdictions.

The Social Services Amendments of 1974 (Public Law 93-647) created Title IV-D and established a federal framework for child support enforcement, initially focused on families receiving Aid to Families with Dependent Children (AFDC). States were required to establish paternity, locate noncustodial parents, and collect support payments.

Subsequent legislation expanded the scope of the program. The Family Support Act of 1988 (Public Law 100-485) extended services to non-welfare families and mandated automated tracking systems for enforcement and collections. The Child Support Performance and Incentive Act of 1998 (Public Law 105-200) created the current incentive structure based on performance metrics.

Over time, enforcement authorities expanded to include wage withholding, tax refund intercepts, license suspensions, and civil contempt sanctions. These tools increased compliance but also blurred traditional distinctions between civil and criminal enforcement mechanisms (Katz, 2019).

Incentive Structure

Federal regulations define five performance measures used to allocate Title IV-D incentive payments.

Table 1

Title IV-D Performance Metrics (Post-1998)

<u>Metric</u>	<u>Formula</u>	<u>Description</u>
Paternity establishment	Percentage of eligible children with legally established paternity	Targets high establishment rates
Support order establishment	Percentage of cases with established support orders	Encourages case processing
Current collections	Current support collected divided by current support owed	Measures payment compliance
Arrearages collections	Arrears collected divided by total arrears owed	Encourages recovery of past-due support
Cost-effectiveness	Total collections divided by program expenditures	Measures administrative efficiency

Gerrish (2017) finds that the 1998 incentive reforms improved performance on the rewarded metrics—particularly paternity establishment and support order establishment—while producing more limited improvements on broader efficiency indicators. Because performance scores are partly influenced by collection levels and caseload volume, incentive structures may

create institutional pressures to maintain active enforcement cases. Custody arrangements that alter the level of support payments may indirectly affect collections-based performance metrics.

Empirical Evidence

If financial incentives influence institutional behavior, one potential pathway would be changes in custody outcomes following modifications to child support guideline structures.

State variation in child support guidelines provides opportunities to examine these dynamics. Fernández Kranz et al. (2021) analyze reforms that provided approximately 40% reductions in child support obligations when joint custody arrangements were adopted. Following these reforms, joint custody awards increased by roughly 10 percentage points. However, the study also found declines in some child health and educational outcomes in households where maternal parenting quality was previously higher, suggesting that economic incentives may influence custody decisions.

A related working paper (Fernández Kranz et al., 2018) reports similar findings and emphasizes the role of economic incentives in shaping parental legal strategies during custody disputes.

Other research examines broader long-term outcomes associated with the formal child support system. Kong et al. (2024) document associations between childhood exposure to the formal child support enforcement system and lower adult earnings in administrative data. These findings reflect correlations rather than direct causal mechanisms and may also capture broader patterns of family instability.

Legal scholarship highlights additional institutional dynamics. Gupta-Kagan (2020) identifies “hidden foster care” arrangements in which child welfare agencies place children with informal kinship caregivers without formal foster care status, partly to avoid administrative

restrictions tied to federal funding rules. These practices illustrate how federal funding structures can shape administrative decisions affecting family arrangements. The Institute for Research on Poverty (2000) describes how enforcement policies affecting low-income families may operate similarly to a financial tax, potentially influencing compliance behavior.

Procedural and Equity Concerns

Legal scholars have raised concerns about procedural safeguards in child support enforcement. Civil enforcement mechanisms increasingly rely on sanctions such as civil contempt that can result in incarceration.

Katz (2019) documents how the enforcement system has evolved in ways that blur traditional distinctions between civil and criminal law. As Katz writes, “The calculated and incomplete conversion of family support enforcement from criminal to civil undercuts the supposedly distinct purposes, procedures, and penalties associated with the civil and criminal categories.”

Cammett (2022) similarly characterizes contemporary child support enforcement as a form of “shadow law” operating outside conventional procedural frameworks.

Other scholars have focused on policy integration challenges. Martin (2015) examines federal proposals linking child support enforcement with parenting time policies and identifies potential unintended consequences. Martin (2016) proposes redirecting portions of Title IV-D funding toward legal assistance and social services for low-income parents.

Policy Analysis Framework

Three broad policy alternatives illustrate potential directions for reform.

Status quo.

The current structure produces more than \$30 billion in annual collections but relies heavily on collection-based performance indicators.

Alternative 1: Incentive recalibration.

One reform option would modify the performance incentive structure by partially replacing collections-based metrics with indicators related to parenting time or shared parenting arrangements. Such changes would likely require federal rulemaking and administrative adjustments.

Alternative 2: Proportional support guidelines.

Another approach would strengthen state guideline formulas that scale support obligations more closely with parenting time. Many states already incorporate parenting-time adjustments in their guidelines.

Alternative 3: Service expansion

A third option would redirect a portion of incentive funding toward employment programs, legal services, or mediation programs for parents involved in the child support system. Evaluations of employment-focused programs such as the Parents' Fair Share initiative suggest potential benefits for payment compliance (Martin, 2016).

Recommendation

A pilot program combining incentive recalibration with proportional support guideline reforms could be implemented in a small number of states. Such a pilot would allow evaluation of potential effects on custody arrangements, child outcomes, and collections stability.

Limitations

This analysis synthesizes published scholarship rather than presenting new empirical data. Establishing causal relationships between Title IV-D incentives and custody outcomes would require access to case-level administrative data linking child support records with custody determinations.

Future research could examine these relationships using state panel data, policy variation across jurisdictions, or pilot program evaluations.

Conclusion

Title IV-D has substantially expanded the capacity of the United States child support enforcement system. The program has achieved high paternity establishment rates and increased national collections to more than \$30 billion annually.

Meanwhile, the incentive structure relies heavily on collection-based performance indicators. These metrics may generate institutional incentives that interact with custody policies and child support guideline structures. Evidence suggests that economic incentives embedded in family law may shape custody decisions, though variation across state contexts may moderate these effects.

Adjusting policies to align child support incentives with shared parenting arrangements could enhance system coherence while maintaining fiscal accountability. Pilot programs testing alternative incentive structures could provide evidence to inform future reforms.

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